

Six species of eupelmid wasps (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea, Eupelmidae) new to Poland and new records of another two species

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ABSTRACT. Six species of parasitoid wasps of the family Eupelmidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) are recorded for the first time from Poland: *Anastatus bifasciatus* (GEOFFROY) and *Eusandalum coronatum* (THOMSON) from Kraków-Wieluń Upland, *Anastatus catalonicus* BOLÍVAR y PIÉLTAİN from Western Beskid, *Eupelmus (Episilindelia) australiensis* (GIRAULT) and *Merostenus excavatus* (DALMAN) from Bieszczady Mts, and *Eupelmus (Macroneura) barai* FUSU from Małopolska Upland. Two species recently recorded as new from Poland, namely *Eupelmus (Eupelmus) kiefferi* DE STEFANI and *Eupelmus (Macroneura) messene* WALKER are documented from Ojców National Park (Kraków-Wieluń Upland). *Calosota agrili* NIKOLSKAYA recorded as new to Poland in 2005 is removed from the Polish list of Eupelmidae. Currently the family Eupelmidae is represented in Poland by 21 species.

KEY WORDS: Chalcidoidea, Eupelmidae, Poland, parasitoids of forest insects, new records, distribution, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

The family Eupelmidae WALKER, 1833 is distributed worldwide. It includes species which are ectoparasites of other insects in either larval or prepupal stages as well as endoparasites or predators of insect or spider eggs (GIBSON 1997). So far, about 1,000 species were described in the world fauna, classified in three subfamilies and 43 extant genera (GIBSON 1989, 1997, NOYES 2021). The family is most diversified in tropical regions. The most species-rich genus is *Eupelmus* DALMAN, 1820 with ca. 340 species described in the world fauna (GIBSON & FUSU 2016, FUSU 2017, NOYES 2021). Generally, the family is poorly studied in Europe. The best studied region is the Iberian Peninsula and Canary Islands where eighty-four species were recorded so far (ASKEW & NIEVES-ALDREY 2017).

The present contribution brings information about six species of the family Eupelmidae new to the Polish fauna. There is also information about new localities for another two species recently recorded from Poland (JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2018, 2020).

The aims of this study are:

- to update the information concerning eupelmid wasps in Poland,
- to fill the gap in the knowledge of the distribution of Eupelmidae in the country,
- to discuss briefly current knowledge of Polish species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens were either collected or reared over quite a long period of time during inventory research of various groups of Hymenoptera in Poland. Most were swept with a net in various habitats. In one case Moericke traps filled with ethylene glycol and water were used. The traps were emptied in ten-days intervals. Some specimens were reared from galls collected usually in January because this allowed to start breeding under laboratory conditions immediately, without additional hibernation or freezing (which already was done under natural conditions). The galls were placed in glass jars covered with dense gauze and kept at room temperature; a few drops of water were added every third day to keep moisture in breeding jars. Emerging insects were collected, killed with ethyl acetate and glued onto triangular mounting cards. The same mounting procedure was applied to specimens collected with entomological net. Specimens were determined by Dr. Lucian Fusu (Romania). The studied specimens are housed in the collection of the first author.

The species are listed in alphabetical order. The zoogeographical division of Poland follows the one accepted in the series “*Katalog Fauny Polski*” (*The Catalogue of Polish Fauna*). For each locality, the UTM code is given. Notes on biology and distribution follow mainly NOYES (2021). The images were taken with Nikon SMZ1270 stereomicroscope with DeltaPix Invenio 12EIII camera with DeltaPix InSight software. Stacks were combined with CombineZP software and then retouched using Adobe Photoshop 2021.

RESULTS

Anastatus bifasciatus (GEOFFROY, 1785)

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [CB72] Góry Towarne near Częstochowa, 12.08.2011, 1 ♂, swept in psammophilous grassland, leg. B. Wiśniowski & A. Jirak.

Distribution (in alphabetical order). Africa: Kenya, Morocco, North Africa; Asia: China, India, Iran, Israel, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kirgizia, Korea, Lebanon, Taiwan, Turkey; Europe: Bosnia and Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy (mainland and Sicily), Moldova, Montenegro, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain (Balearics), Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine; North America: United States of America (NOYES 2021, SAMIN *et al.* 2019, STAHL *et al.* 2019). *Anastatus bifasciatus* was mentioned by CROSSMAN (1925) from ‘Schlesien, Germany’ and ‘Huszt, which is in Poland’. The first locality is too general to be attributed to any Polish part of Silesia, and the second locality is in present Ukraine.

Biology: Parasitoid in eggs of insects from various orders: Hemiptera (families: Aphididae LATREILLE, 1802, Coreidae LEACH, 1815, Pentatomidae LEACH, 1815, Psyllidae LATREILLE, 1807, Scutelleridae LEACH, 1815), Lepidoptera (families: Lasiocampidae HARRIS, 1841, Lymantriidae HAMPSON, 1893, Notodontidae STEPHENS, 1829, Nymphalidae RAFINESQUE, 1815, Papilionidae LATREILLE, 1802, Saturniidae BOISDUVAL, 1837, Sphingidae LATREILLE, 1802), and Orthoptera (families: Acrididae MACLEAY, 1819, Tettigoniidae KRAUSS, 1902), as well as hymenopteran hosts of the family Braconidae LATREILLE, 1829 (NOYES 2021).

Anastatus catalonicus BOLÍVAR y PIELTAIN, 1935 (Figs. 1, 2)

Western Beskid: [DV89] Kamionka Wielka, 12.06.2018, 1 ♀, collected on wooden wall of old house, ca. 560 m a.s.l., leg. B. Wiśniowski.

Distribution (in alphabetical order). Asia: Iran; Europe: Bulgaria, France, Germany, Romania, Spain (mainland, Balearics, Canary Islands) (LOTFALIZADEH & PARSA 2018, NOYES 2021).

Fig. 1. *Anastatus catalonicus*, female, lateral view. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Ryc. 1. *Anastatus catalonicus*, samica, widok z boku. Skala = 0,5 mm.

Fig. 2. *Anastatus catalonicus*, female, head and mesosoma, dorsal view. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Ryc. 2. *Anastatus catalonicus*, samica, głowa i tułów, widok z góry. Skala = 0,5 mm.

Biology: Known hosts are in the order Lepidoptera (*Lymantria dispar* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Lymantriidae), and Mantodea (*Iris oratoria* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Mantidae BURMEISTER, 1838)). The gall wasp *Biorhiza pallida* (OLIVIER, 1791) (Hymenoptera: Cynipidae LATREILLE, 1802) is listed as an associate (NOYES 2021).

Eupelmus (Episolindelia) australiensis (GIRAULT, 1913) (Fig. 3)

Bieszczady Mts: [FV14] Bieszczady National Park, Berehy Górne, 28.07.2000, 1 ♀, swept on meadow located ca. 850 m a.s.l., leg. B. Wiśniowski.

Distribution: Distributed worldwide except Antarctica. In Europe known from Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Serbia, Slovakia, and Ukraine (NOYES 2021).

Biology: Parasitoid of insects of orders Diptera (various species of the genus *Contarinia* RÓNDANI, 1860 (Cecidomyiidae NEWMAN, 1835), and Lepidoptera (*Nola cereella* (BOSC, 1800) (Nolidae BRUAND, 1847). *Aprostocetus diplosidis* CRAWFORD, 1907 and *Tetrastichus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae WESTWOOD, 1829) are listed as parasitoid hosts (NOYES 2021).

Fig. 3. *Eupelmus (Episolindelia) australiensis*, female, lateral view. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Ryc. 3. *Eupelmus (Episolindelia) australiensis*, samica, widok z boku. Skala = 0,5 mm.

Eupelmus (Macroneura) barai FUSU, 2017 (Fig. 4)

Małopolska Upland: [DB62] Chęciny, 9.04.1994, 6 ♀♀, reared from flowerheads of *Centaurea stoebe* L., and 2 ♀♀ reared from galls of *Diplolepis rosae* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Hymenoptera: Cynipidae) on *Rosa canina* L., leg. & cult. B. Wiśniowski.

Distribution (in alphabetical order). Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Romania, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland (NOYES 2021).

Biology: Parasitoid of species from various insect orders: Coleoptera (*Scolytus rugulosus* (MUELLER, 1818) (Curculionidae LATREILLE, 1802: Scolytinae LATREILLE, 1804), Diptera (families: Cecidomyiidae, Tephritidae NEWMAN, 1834), Hymenoptera (numerous gall wasps of the family Cynipidae, *Neodiprion sertifer* (GEOFFROY, 1785) (Diprionidae ROHWER, 1911), *Bruchophagus roddi* GUSSAKOVSKIY, 1933, *Tetramesa brevicornis* (WALKER, 1832), *T. cylindrica* (SCHLECHTENDAL 1891) (Eurytomidae WALKER, 1832)), Lepidoptera (*Millieria dolosalis* (HEYDENREICH, 1851) (Millieriidae STANTON, 1854), *Coleophora silenella* HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1855 (Coleophoridae HÜBNER, 1825), *Rhyacionia buoliana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775) (Tortricidae LATREILLE, 1803), *Yponomeuta cagnagella* (HÜBNER, 1813) and *Y. malinellus* ZELLER, 1838 (Yponomeutidae STEPHENS, 1829) (NOYES 2021). The cynipid gall wasp *Diplolepis rosae* seems to be the new host for *E. barai*.

Fig. 4. *Eupelmus (Macroneura) barai*, female, lateral view. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Ryc. 4. *Eupelmus (Macroneura) barai*, samica, widok z boku. Skala = 0,5 mm.

Eusandalum coronatum (THOMSON, 1876) (Figs. 5, 6)

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [DA16] Ojców National Park, Ojców-Czyżówki, 7-17.06.2003, 1 ♀, collected in Moericke trap on edge of oak-hornbeam forest (*Tilio-Carpinetum*), leg. B. Wiśniowski.

Distribution (in alphabetical order). Europe: Austria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Russia (European part), Spain, Sweden (NOYES 2021).

Biology: *E. coronatum* was reported as a parasitoid of larvae of the genus *Anthaxia* ESCHSCHOLTZ, 1829 (Coleoptera: Buprestidae LEACH, 1815), and *Magdalis* GERMAR, 1817 (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) (NOYES 2021).

Fig. 5. *Eusandalum coronatum*, female, dorsal view. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Ryc. 5. *Eusandalum coronatum*, samica, widok z góry. Skala = 0,5 mm.

Fig. 6. *Eusandalum coronatum*, female, head and mesosoma, dorsal view. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Ryc. 6. *Eusandalum coronatum*, samica, głowa i tułów, widok z góry. Skala = 0,5 mm.

Merostenus excavatus (DALMAN, 1820) (Fig. 7)

Bieszczady Mts: [FV14] Bieszczady National Park, Berehy Górne, 28.07.2000, 1 ♀, swept on meadow situated ca. 850 m a.s.l., leg. B. Wiśniowski.

Distribution (in alphabetical order). Europe: Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain (Balearics), Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom; North America: United States of America (NOYES 2021).

Biology: Known as a parasitoid of *Hypera postica* (GYLLENHAL, 1813) larvae (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) (NOYES 2021).

Fig. 7. *Merostenus excavatus*, female, lateral view; antennae partly damaged. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Ryc. 7. *Merostenus excavatus*, samica, widok z boku; czułki częściowo uszkodzone. Skala = 0,5 mm.

New records:

Eupelmus (Eupelmus) kiefferi DE STEFANI, 1898

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [DA16] Ojców National Park, Ojców, serpentine road, 22.02.1997, 1 ♀, reared from stems of *Crepis biennis* L., leg. B. Wiśniowski.

Eupelmus kiefferi was recorded from Poland by JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2018) from Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, [XU51] Promno ad Poznań, and [XT29] Puszczykowo ad Poznań, as well as from Lower Silesia: [XS29] Strupina ad Żmigród, [XS36] Wrocław Popowice, and [XS37] Wrocław Świniary. Most specimens were either swept on various plants or reared from galls during 2008-2017; a few were also reared from fruit of *Sorbus aucuparia* L. inhabited by *Megastigmus brevicaudis* RATZEBURG, 1852 (Hymenoptera: Torymidae WALKER, 1833).

***Eupelmus (Macroneura) messene* WALKER, 1839**

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: [DA16] Ojców National Park, Ojców, serpentine road, 22.02.1997, 1 ♀, reared from stems of *Crepis biennis*, leg. B. Wiśniowski.

Eupelmus messene was recorded from Poland by JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2020) from Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, and from Lower Silesia: [XS34] Rolantowice. The specimens were collected in 2018. According to FUSU (2017), this species is a parasitoid of various insects living in stems of plants.

Both *E. kiefferi* and *E. messene* were reared from the same stems of *Crepis biennis* with inner galls caused by an unknown galls wasp of the genus *Phanacis* FOERSTER, 1860 (Hymenoptera: Cynipidae) collected in Ojców National Park.

DISCUSSION

The first checklist of the family Eupelmidae of Poland was published in 1997 (WIŚNIEWSKI 1997) and included 11 species. There was *Eupelmus sculpturatus* NIKOLSKAYA, 1952 among the species which is a junior synonym of *Eupelmus pini* TAYLOR, 1927. Since then, a few contributions were published with new records for the country: WIŚNIEWSKI & MIŁKOWSKI 2005 (new record of *Calosota agrili* NIKOLSKAYA, 1952), WIŚNIEWSKI & GUTOWSKI 2007 (*Calosota aestivalis* CURTIS, 1836), JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2018 (*Eupelmus azureus* RATZEBURG, 1844 and *E. kiefferi* DE STEFANI, 1898), and JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2020 (*Eupelmus messene* WALKER, 1839). After verification of specimens identified previously as *Calosota agrili* it turned out that they represent *C. aestivalis*. As a result, *C. agrili* should be removed from the Polish checklist. Currently, 21 species of eupelmid wasps are known to occur in Poland.

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Streszczenie

Sześć gatunków bleskotek z rodziny Eupelmidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) nowych w faunie Polski i nowe dane o występowaniu dwu kolejnych przedstawicieli tej rodziny

W pracy podano po raz pierwszy informacje o sześciu gatunkach z rodziny Eupelmidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) stwierdzonych w faunie Polski: *Anastatus bifasciatus* (GEOFFROY) i *Eusandalum coronatum* (THOMSON) z Wyżyny Krakowsko-Wieluńskiej, *Anastatus catalonicus* BOLÍVAR y PIeltaIN z Beskidu Zachodniego, *Eupelmus* (*Episolindelia*) *australiensis* (GIRAULT) i *Merostenus excavatus* (DALMAN) z Bieszczadzkiego Parku Narodowego (Bieszczady), oraz *Eupelmus* (*Macroneura*) *barai* FUSU z Wyżyny Małopolskiej. Dwa kolejne gatunki z tej rodziny stwierdzone ostatnio po raz pierwszy w faunie Polski, a mianowicie *Eupelmus* (*Eupelmus*) *kiefferi* DE STEFANI i *Eupelmus* (*Macroneura*) *messene* WALKER zostały stwierdzone w Ojcowskim Parku Narodowym (Wyżyna Krakowsko-Wieluńska). W wyniku korekty oznaczeń gatunek *Calosota agrili* NIKOLSKAYA odnotowany w 2005 roku zostaje skreślony z listy krajowych Eupelmidae. Obecnie, uwzględniając dane z obecnej publikacji, rodzina ta jest reprezentowana w Polsce przez 21 gatunków.

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